

Optimization of Lead Placement in the Right Ventricle During Cardiac Resynchronization Therapy. A Simulation Study

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13 **Keywords:** cardiac resynchronization therapy, heart failure, LBBB, computational modeling, QRS
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15 Abstract

16 Patients suffering from heart failure and left bundle branch block show electrical ventricular
17 dyssynchrony causing an abnormal blood pumping. Cardiac resynchronization therapy (CRT) is
18 recommended for these patients. Patients with positive therapy response normally present QRS
19 shortening and an increased left ventricle (LV) ejection fraction. However, around one third do not
20 respond favorably. Therefore, optimal location of pacing leads, timing delays between leads and/or
21 choosing related biomarkers is crucial to achieve the best possible degree of ventricular synchrony
22 during CRT application. In this study, computational modeling is used to predict the optimal location
23 and delay of pacing leads to improve CRT response. We use a 3D electrophysiological computational
24 model of the heart and torso to get insight into the changes in the activation patterns obtained when the
25 heart is paced from different regions and for different atrioventricular and interventricular delays. The
26 model represents a heart with left bundle branch block and heart failure, and allows a detailed and
27 accurate analysis of the electrical changes observed simultaneously in the myocardium and in the QRS
28 complex computed in the precordial leads. Computational simulations were performed using a
29 modified version of the O'Hara et al. action potential model, the most recent mathematical model
30 developed for human ventricular electrophysiology. The optimal location for the pacing leads was
31 determined by QRS maximal reduction. Additionally, the influence of Purkinje system on CRT
32 response was assessed and correlation analysis between several parameters of the QRS was made.
33 Simulation results showed that the right ventricle (RV) upper septum near the outflow tract is an
34 alternative location to the RV apical lead. Furthermore, LV endocardial pacing provided better results
35 as compared to epicardial stimulation. Finally, the time to reach the 90% of the QRS area was a good
36 predictor of the instant at which 90% of the ventricular tissue was activated. Thus, the time to reach

37 the 90% of the QRS area is suggested as an additional index to assess CRT effectiveness to improve
38 biventricular synchrony.

39 1 Introduction

40 Heart failure (HF) constitutes a major public health problem worldwide and much attention has been
41 paid to the understanding of the arrhythmogenic mechanisms in the failing heart induced by the
42 structural, electrical, and metabolic remodeling. Heart failure is also characterized by a compromised
43 ventricular contraction, which is fundamental for an optimal cardiac function. Lack of synchrony in
44 heart contraction is worsened when the failing heart is also affected by left bundle branch block
45 (LBBB). These patients present electrical and mechanical ventricular dyssynchrony causing pump
46 dysfunction, reduced functional capacity, and myocardial remodeling. In particular, LBBB is
47 associated with delayed contraction of the left ventricle (LV), reduced ventricular performance and
48 widening of the QRS complex.

49 The relative QRS duration (QRSd) provides a powerful prognostic value for patients with HF and is a
50 primary indicator of eligibility for cardiac resynchronization therapy (CRT). CRT helps to reduce
51 mortality and morbidity associated with HF (Abraham et al., 2002; Cleland et al., 2005). Recent studies
52 have also concluded that patients with LBBB are more likely to respond to CRT than those with right
53 bundle branch block (RBBB) or nonspecific interventricular conduction delays (IVCDs) (Zareba et al.,
54 2011).

55 During CRT, two synchronized electrical stimuli are usually delivered to reduce ventricular
56 dyssynchrony. One stimulation lead is usually placed on the apex of the right ventricle (RV), and the
57 other one on the epicardium of the LV lateral wall. Patients with positive therapy response present
58 QRS shortening and an increased LV ejection fraction (LVEF) (Bonakdar et al., 2009; Coppola et al.,
59 2016; Zhang et al., 2015). However, around one third of the patients do not respond favorably to this
60 therapy (Bertaglia et al., 2017; Linde et al., 2012) and implantation issues, such as perforation of the
61 RV apex, have been observed.

62 Optimal location of pacing leads is crucial to achieve the best degree of ventricular synchrony. LV lead
63 position has been recognized as an important determinant for response to CRT since the initial
64 development of this therapy (Crozier et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2011). Experimental
65 studies and computational models (Lopez-Perez et al., 2015) have been used to optimize LV lead
66 location. In current guidelines (Brignole et al., 2013), the LV posterior-lateral wall is the recommended
67 LV region for CRT application. Several studies have reported the beneficial results of pacing from the
68 lateral region of the LV (Rossillo et al., 2004). However, there are still several open questions.

69 First, as suggested by Zanon et al. the ideal LV lead placement should be the latest electrical intrinsic
70 activated region (Zanon et al., 2014), typically the postero-lateral wall (Şipal et al., 2018). This location
71 provided the maximum increase in contractility, expressed as the highest value of the first derivative
72 of LV pressure over time ($LV \, dP/dt_{max}$). However, the electromechanical modelling study by Pluijmer
73 et al. (Pluijmer et al., 2016) determined that in fascicular block conditions the latest activated area did
74 not provide the maximum response in contractility. A different criterion suggested in the literature is
75 to place the LV lead in the site corresponding to the shortest QRS registered. Nevertheless, simulation
76 studies that apply this last non-invasive criterion (Miri et al., 2009a, 2009b) estimated QRSd through
77 calculation of the total ventricular activation time (TAT), a parameter not easily accessible in clinical
78 or even experimental settings. In addition, studies such as Potse et al. (Potse et al., 2012) have observed

79 that biventricular pacing did not change QRS duration but reduced total ventricular activation time
80 when the stimulation was applied in one point of the LV free wall.

81 Second, there is controversy about whether a higher degree of synchrony can be achieved by
82 stimulating from points in the RV other than the apex (Da Costa et al., 2013; Pastore et al., 2013).
83 Third, individualized programming of the atrioventricular delay (AVD) and interventricular delay
84 (VVD) intervals is not typically performed in most patients in the normal clinical practice, and it has
85 been primarily reserved for non CRT responders (Gras et al., 2009). The largest trials studying CRT
86 used various methods to optimize these intervals, most frequently based on echocardiography and
87 intracardiac electrogram interval measurements, but unequivocal proof of the benefit brought by
88 optimization is still lacking (Abraham et al., 2010; Brugada et al., 2014; Krum et al., 2012).
89 Echocardiography presents inherent variability of results and is highly operator dependent.
90 Optimization based on intracardiac electrogram intervals has not proved yet to be of clear benefit above
91 arbitrary atrioventricular interval (Ulč and Vančura, 2013). Another optimization method based on the
92 surface ECG uses fusion with intrinsic conduction and avoids echocardiographic atrioventricular and
93 biventricular optimization (Arbelo et al., 2014). Applying this method Arbelo et al. determined that
94 electrocardiographic optimization improved invasive LV dp/dt_{max} . Similarly, randomized studies
95 demonstrated that electrocardiographic optimization had superior LV remodeling at 6-month follow
96 up although survival was not different, compared with optimization by echocardiography (Bertini et
97 al., 2008; Tamborero et al., 2011). All these results suggest that minimizing QRSd could be used as a
98 non-invasive method to optimize CRT.

99 In this study, we used a 3D biophysical model of the heart and torso to optimize pacing leads location,
100 AVD, and VVD settings during CRT procedure, based on the shortest QRS duration measured on the
101 torso surface. Results were compared with other optimization criteria. This analysis was used to define
102 an electrical biomarker that relates the optimal lead configuration with the observed surface
103 electrocardiogram signals.

104 **2 Methods**

105 **2.1 Anatomical model**

106 A 3D biventricular model of the heart was built from segmentation of a DE-MRI images stack. The
107 cardiac DE-MRI was acquired from the Hospital Clinic Universitari de Valencia (Valencia, Spain).
108 Regarding the ethical considerations, the protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee for Clinical
109 Research of the Hospital Clinic Universitari de Valencia, which certifies that the present study was
110 conducted in accordance with the recommendations gathered in the Declaration of Helsinki, originally
111 adopted by the General Assembly of the World Medical Association in 1964, and in its subsequent
112 revisions. Furthermore, the patient, who underwent the standard clinical protocol, gave written
113 informed consent for the use of his anonymized clinical data in this study.

114 Manual image segmentation was performed using Seg3D software (Scientific Computing and Imaging
115 Institute, University of Utah, USA) (Seg3D, 2013), including papillary muscles and main endocardial
116 trabeculations (Figure 1 (A)). From the segmented DE-MRI stack, a surface model of the ventricles
117 was generated and subsequently meshed using MeshGems-Hexa (Distene S.A.S., Bruyeres-le-Chatel,
118 France), obtaining a hexahedra-based volume mesh comprised of 4 million nodes (vertices) and 3.71
119 million elements, with an average edge length of 0.4 mm (see supplementary material for further
120 detailed information). Transmural heterogeneity (Figure 1 (B)) was defined by three different
121 transmural layers for endocardial (blue), midmyocardial (green), and epicardial (red) cells within the

122 volume mesh of our ventricular model, spanning 17%, 41%, and 42% of ventricular wall thickness,
123 respectively (Desk et al., 1998; Sicouri et al., 1994; Sicouri and Antzelevitch, 1991).

124 To include the anisotropy of the cardiac muscle through fibers orientation (Figure 1 (C)), we
125 implemented Streeter's rule-based method (Streeter, 1979) modeled by the set of equations described
126 in (Sebastian et al., 2009) defining the helix (α_h) and transmural (α_t) angles. In papillary muscles and
127 endocardial trabeculations, fibers are known to be aligned parallel to the longitudinal axis of those
128 anatomical structures (Greenbaum et al., 1981). In order to reproduce such configuration, we
129 performed the topological skeletonization of the volume mesh to extract the medial axes of each one
130 of those structures, what enabled to properly assign the fiber orientation. Finally, we performed a
131 Gaussian smoothing with a 3D kernel to soften abrupt transitions in fibers direction between the
132 myocardial wall and the papillary muscles and trabeculations.

133 A Purkinje system (PS) network (Figure 1 (D, E)) was developed based on a stochastic grown method
134 (Sebastian et al., 2013) formed by linear elements. The RV section was composed of two main
135 branches, one descending to the apex, and another extending to the surroundings of the moderator
136 band, with several subdivisions. The LV section was formed by three main branches with several
137 subdivisions: one descending to the apex towards the papillary muscles of the lateral wall, another one
138 to the anterior wall, and the last one to the posterior wall. The location of the PMJs that start the
139 endocardial activation from the main PS branches was optimized to obtain a typical ECG wave
140 morphology in the precordial leads. Purkinje-Myocardial junctions (PMJs) conductivity were adjusted
141 to allow retrograde and anterograde electrical propagation. A total of 1391 PMJ were distributed across
142 the RV and LV.

143 The biventricular mesh was fit into a human torso mesh (Ferrer et al., 2015) to be able to properly solve
144 the forward problem in electrophysiology and simulate the electrocardiogram (ECG) (Figure 1 (F)).
145 The torso dataset was obtained from the online open repository at the Centre for Integrative Biomedical
146 Computing (CBIC) from University of Utah (MacLeod et al., 1991). The torso volume mesh was made
147 of tetrahedral elements of 0.5 mm spatial resolution. Note that the problem of passive propagation of
148 extracellular potentials, i.e. only diffusion without reaction component, does not require such a fine
149 spatial resolution outside the heart domain (Prassl et al., 2009); for this reason, the torso mesh is highly
150 refined only in the region where it intersects with the ventricles (see supplementary material for
151 complementary description).

152 **2.2 Electrophysiological model**

153 O'Hara et al. (O'Hara et al., 2011) model is the most recent action potential model developed for human
154 ventricular electrophysiology. Our simulations were conducted using a modified version of this model
155 to achieve realistic conduction velocity and electrical propagation in 3D ventricular tissue. For this
156 reason, the original fast sodium current (I_{Na}) formulation was modified. Firstly, the steady state
157 inactivation (h_{ss} and j_{ss}) and activation (m_{ss}) gates were changed as in Passini et al. (Passini et al., 2016)
158 and Mora et al. (Mora et al., 2017), respectively. Secondly, the time constant of the inactivation gates
159 was modified as in Dutta et al. (Dutta et al., 2017). Finally, the sodium conductance (G_{Na}) was
160 decreased to 23% of its original value to obtain approximately a maximum upstroke velocity (dV/dt_{max})
161 of 260 V/ms as in the original O'Hara et al. (O'Hara et al., 2011) model. Furthermore, the late sodium
162 current (I_{NaL}) conductance (G_{NaL}) was duplicated to maintain the relationship between I_{NaL} and peak
163 I_{Na} observed in voltage-clamp experiments as described in Mora et al. (Mora et al., 2017). All these
164 changes are detailed in the supplementary material together with the action potential (Figure S1)

165 obtained with the original and modified O'Hara et al. models. The action potential model for Purkinje
 166 cells developed by Stewart et al. (Stewart et al., 2009) was used in the cardiac conduction system.

167 The electrical propagation through the ventricles was calculated by solving the monodomain equation
 168 (Equation. 1) using ELVIRA FEM software (Heidenreich et al., 2010),

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{D}\nabla V_m) = C_m \frac{\partial V_m}{\partial t} + I_{ion} + I_{stim} \quad (1)$$

169 where \mathbf{D} is the equivalent conductivity tensor, V_m the transmembrane potential field, C_m the cell
 170 membrane capacitance, I_{ion} the transmembrane ionic current and I_{stim} the transmembrane stimulation
 171 current.

172 The ECG was simulated by solving the extracellular potential φ_e from the equation

$$\nabla \cdot ([D_i + D_e]\nabla\varphi_e) = -\nabla \cdot (D_i\nabla V_m) \quad (2)$$

173 where D_i and D_e are the volume-average conductivity tensors of the intra and extracellular domains ,
 174 respectively (Potse et al., 2006). The reaction-diffusion simulation was run on the biventricular mesh.
 175 The right-hand side of Equation 2 was evaluated on this fine mesh and then interpolated on the coarser
 176 torso mesh. The extracellular potential φ_e was solved on the coarser mesh. The precordial ECG leads
 177 were then computed by extracting the extracellular potential at the electrode locations taking into
 178 account the Wilson terminal, as in clinical practice (see supplementary material).

179 In order to establish the conductivities that will define the conduction velocities (CV) in the heart
 180 domain, we performed a set of test simulations on a 3D slab model (20x20x6 mm) composed of regular
 181 hexahedral elements (voxels) with an edge length of 0.4 mm, matching the average length in the
 182 ventricular model. As a result, we set the conductivity values to 0.5 S/m and 0.1 S/m for longitudinal
 183 (σ_L) and transversal (σ_T) conductivity, respectively. This resulted in a CV of 0.61 m/s along the fiber
 184 direction and of 0.29 m/s in transverse direction. These values are consistent with experimental
 185 measurements in human ventricles (Taggart et al., 2000).

186 CV in the PS was adjusted to 2.5 m/s (Durrer et al., 1970; Dux-santoy et al., 2012). The electrical
 187 propagation in the torso mesh was considered isotropic and specific conductivities were assigned to
 188 each organ: i) myocardium (4.589 mS/cm), ii) bones (0.200 mS/cm), iii) liver (0.277 mS/cm), iv) lungs
 189 (0.389 mS/cm), v) muscle (2.390 mS/cm), and vi) blood (7.0 mS/cm) based on several experimental
 190 studies (Bradley et al., 1997; Keller et al., 2010; Roth, 1992).

191 **2.3 Pathological model**

192 To simulate LBBB, an electrical block was generated on the left section of the PS before the bifurcation
 193 into three sub-branches by imposing null conductivity in two linear elements (see Figure 1 (D)). HF
 194 condition was modeled by a reduction of 50% in CV, in accordance with protein connexin43 (Cx43)
 195 reduction observed in failing tissue (Coronel et al., 2013). The decrease and lateralization of this protein
 196 is associated with reduced longitudinal conduction velocity (Ai and Pogwizd, 2005; Akar et al., 2007;
 197 Wang and Hill, 2010).

198 **2.4 Stimulation protocols**

199 For the present study a 3D anatomical model of the ventricles was generated, which does not include
200 the geometry of the atria. Therefore, the intrinsic activation from the sinoatrial node was simulated by
201 applying an electrical stimulus to the His bundle, either in healthy or HF + LBBB conditions (see
202 Figure 1 (D)). CRT leads were modeled as 0.5 mm^3 cubes injecting a transmembrane current of 400
203 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{F}$ in amplitude (see Equation 1). Four scenarios of CRT pacing were defined for HF + LBBB
204 conditions with different combinations of atrioventricular delay (AVD) and interventricular delay
205 (VVD) for each lead location configuration (AVD = 100 ms, VVD = 0 ms; AVD = 100 ms, VVD = 30
206 ms; AVD = 140 ms, VVD = 0 ms; AVD = 140 ms, VVD = 30 ms).

207 AVD is the time delay between the instant of initial activation of the sinoatrial node (external or
208 intrinsic stimulation) and the instant of time of external CRT stimulation of the ventricles. To set the
209 value of AVD in our simulations, several considerations were taken into account. Firstly, the typical
210 duration of PR interval observed in LBBB patients is 200 ms (Rickard et al., 2017), which is the time
211 that takes the initial atrial stimulation to spread through the atria (100 ms), plus the time delay in the
212 atrioventricular (AV) node (80 ms) (Prinzen and Vernooy, 2017), plus the propagation time from the
213 His bundle through Purkinje system to finally reach the first activation site of the ventricles (20 ms
214 approximately). Secondly, our model does not include the atria or the AV node as mentioned before,
215 so that the intrinsic activation was simulated by stimulating His bundle, which is included in our 3D
216 model.

217 In our simulations, different AVDs could be simulated by changing the stimulation time of the His
218 bundle (coming from the intrinsic activation of the atria). Thus, an AVD of 100 ms was modeled by
219 applying an electrical stimulus to the His bundle of 80 ms after ventricular leads activation. Indeed,
220 when we applied the external CRT ventricular stimulation, 100 ms after initial activation of the
221 sinoatrial node (AVD of 100 ms), this intrinsic activation had reached the atrial side of the AV node
222 (this takes 100 ms) and needed still 80 ms to reach His bundle (delay needed in the AV node). In the
223 case of an AVD of 140 ms, the electrical stimulus in the His bundle was applied 40 ms after ventricular
224 leads activation. Indeed, when we applied the external CRT ventricular stimulation, 140 ms after initial
225 activation of the sinoatrial node, this intrinsic activation had reached the AV node in 100 ms and 40
226 ms of delay in the AV have also elapsed, the stimulus needed 40 ms more to reach the His bundle, and
227 this is why we stimulated the His bundle 40 ms after the ventricles. Additionally, VVD was set to 0 ms
228 (stimulation in both ventricles simultaneously) and 30 ms (the RV was stimulated 30 ms after the LV),
229 according to the time ranges used in clinical practice (Brignole et al., 2013; Urbanek et al., 2017).

230 **2.5 Leads location**

231 The RV septal wall is an alternative location for the RV pacing lead in CRT. In this study, three
232 different locations for the RV pacing lead were tested based on medical protocols and research works
233 (Da Costa et al., 2013; Pastore et al., 2013). The RV septal electrode was placed in the apex (RVapex),
234 middle septal region (RVmid) or upper region near the outflow tract (RVupper) (Figure 2 (A)).

235 For the LV pacing lead location, the LV free wall was divided into three different regions (Dou et al.,
236 2012; Singh et al., 2011): anterior, lateral, and posterior (Figure 2 (B)). In addition, each region was
237 divided into three segments: apical, mid-cavity, and basal, leading to a set of nine segments for the LV
238 free wall as illustrated in Figure 2 (C) as in Singh et al. (Singh et al., 2011). The LV pacing lead was
239 placed in the middle of each segment, both in the epicardial (Figure 2 (C)) and endocardial wall (Figure
240 2 (D)) to represent and simplify the different possible positions of the electrode within the same region,
241 due to variety of veins configurations observed in CRT patients.

242 To summarize, we have a total of 54 lead location configurations obtained by combination of the three
243 RV lead locations with eighteen LV lead locations (9 epicardial and 9 endocardial) for the application
244 of the CRT protocol.

245 **2.6 QRS measurements**

246 QRS complex was computed in the precordial leads location on the torso surface for each CRT
247 configuration and QRSd was measured using an algorithm implemented in Matlab software
248 (Mathworks Inc., Natick, MA, USA). This algorithm determines the beginning and end of the QRS
249 complex based on the first and second derivate of the electrocardiographic signal (see Figure S2 in the
250 supplementary material). The QRS onset was calculated applying a threshold in the first derivate to
251 determine a change in the slope. To estimate the end of QRS complex, additional signal processing
252 was required as baseline was not reached in most CRT configurations. A time interval after the QRS
253 complex was set based on the 95% of the accumulated area under the curve of the second derivate, and
254 the end of the signal. To set the end of the QRS, the lowest value of the first derivate was used within
255 this interval (see supplementary material for details). Once the beginning and end of QRS complex
256 were determined for each precordial lead, the QRSd was calculated as the time interval between the
257 onset beginning and the latest end of the QRS among all leads (Surawicz et al., 2009). This is the
258 recommended criterion by the American Heart Association, the American College of Cardiology
259 Foundation, and the Heart Rhythm Society (AHA/ACC/HRS). The total activation time (TAT) of the
260 ventricular mesh was estimated as the time interval between the first and last depolarized node mesh
261 above a threshold of -10 mV.

262 **2.7 Correlation analysis**

263 Shortest QRSd was the criterion applied to evaluate the optimal location of the LV lead for different
264 positions of the pacing lead in the RV. However, the total activation time (TAT), QRS area (QRSa)
265 and the time to 90% of activated tissue (t_{90}) are other important parameters that have been used to
266 evaluate CRT response. For this reason, three linear correlations between these parameters were
267 performed using Pearson correlation method. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically
268 significant. Values for the analysis are shown in Tables S1-S5 in the supplementary material.

269 **3 Results**

270 **3.1 Model validation**

271 Simulated ventricular activation maps for non-pathological and HF conditions with LBBB (HF +
272 LBBB) are shown in Figure 3 (A). In healthy conditions, the electrical impulse traveled from the bundle
273 of His to the first activation point in the LV endocardium in approximately 20 ms. RV activation started
274 10 ms after the onset of LV activation (Durrer et al., 1970). The computed time until all the ventricular
275 tissue was depolarized (total activation time or TAT) was approximately 103 ms, in accordance with
276 human data (Boukens et al., 2014). The outflow tract and the posterobasal area were the last activated
277 regions in the RV, while the latest areas depolarized in the LV were the anterior mid and basal regions.

278 Under HF + LBBB conditions, activation began in the RV endocardium and reached the LV
279 endocardium in the apical septal region after 46 ms from the onset of the LV depolarization. This is in
280 agreement with the data recorded experimentally by Auricchio et al. (Auricchio et al., 2004). The last
281 activated region in the LV was the lateral wall in accordance with the study of Rad et al. (Mafi Rad et
282 al., 2014). Additionally, the TAT was increased in 104% compared to a healthy heart.

283 Figure 3 (B) shows the computed QRS complexes in the precordial leads for simulations in a healthy
284 heart and under HF + LBBB conditions. For non-pathological conditions, QRS duration (QRSd) was
285 93 ms, while in HF + LBBB QRSd was increased to 190 ms. Both values are within experimental
286 ranges (Spragg et al., 2010; Tian et al., 2017). Additionally, QRS complexes in HF + LBBB simulations
287 present an rS pattern (small R wave followed by a bigger S wave) (Sweeney et al., 2014) in leads V1
288 and V2 and a mid-QRS notching in several leads. These observations are in agreement with the criteria
289 proposed by Strauss et al. (Strauss et al., 2011) to define complete LBBB.

290 3.2 QRS duration during CRT

291 A total of 54 electrode placement configurations with four different delays (two AVD and two VVD
292 configurations) settings were tested for the CRT simulations. QRSd values are shown in Table S1.

293 Figure 4 compares the simulated QRS complexes in a scenario with HF + LBBB before (red traces)
294 and after (green traces) the application of the CRT protocol. The optimal configurations in terms of
295 shortest QRSd for the RV lead placement tested (apex, mid septum, and upper septum) are shown in
296 the different rows. Epicardial versus endocardial LV lead stimulation for those configurations are
297 shown in columns.

298 Firstly, we analyzed the optimal lead placement. The shortest QRSd among all configurations tested
299 was obtained when the RV lead was placed in the upper septum near the outflow track (third row).
300 Furthermore, for all RV lead placement the optimal location of the LV lead, both in the epicardium
301 and endocardium, was the LV mid posterior wall.

302 Secondly, we analyzed the effect of the delay between pacing leads and intrinsic activation in a fixed
303 location. The best configurations for the RV lead placed in the apex are depicted in the first row. QRSd
304 was reduced from 172 ms (Figure 4 (A)) to 157 ms (Figure 4 (B)), but bigger reductions were obtained
305 for different intrinsic and pacing delays (AVD = 140 ms, VVD = 0 ms; AVD = 100 ms, VVD = 30 ms,
306 respectively).

307 When the RV lead was located in the middle of the septum (second row), the QRSd was reduced from
308 161 ms (Figure 4 (C)) to 146 ms (Figure 4 (D)) for optimal configurations. In this case, these results
309 were obtained for different pacing delays between leads but the same AVD (AVD = 140 ms and VVD
310 = 30 ms vs AVD = 140 ms and VVD = 0 ms, respectively).

311 If the RV lead was placed in the upper septum, the QRSd was reduced from 149 ms (Figure 4 (E)) to
312 143 ms (Figure 4 (F)). However, in this case both configurations were achieved with the same intrinsic
313 and biventricular delay (AVD = 140 ms, VVD = 30 ms).

314 Finally, the influence of LV epicardial versus endocardial pacing was assessed. QRSd was decreased
315 in all cases after CRT application, but the reduction was greater for LV leads placed in the endocardium
316 (column 2) compared to epicardium (column 1).

317 Summarizing, the optimal location in terms of shortest QRSd was obtained when the RV lead was
318 placed in the upper septum and the LV lead was located in the mid posterior wall region. Once the
319 optimal lead location was selected for both RV and LV leads, the shortest QRSd was measured for
320 different intrinsic and biventricular delays, without highlighting a particular optimal setting. Finally,
321 the shortest QRSd was obtained in all configurations when the LV lead was placed in the endocardium
322 compared with those in the epicardium.

3.3 Ventricular activation time during CRT

Another helpful parameter to assess CRT outcome is the total activation time (TAT) of the ventricles. This parameter is not directly accessible in clinical practice during CRT procedures, but simulations can provide additional information to achieve the ideal configuration. Ideally, within normal physiological ranges, the shorter the QRS the shorter TAT, leading to an increase in ventricular synchrony. In Figure 5, the percentage of activated ventricular tissue is shown as a function of time for the healthy heart, under HF + LBBB conditions, and for the optimal CRT configurations (as a function of RV location), which are shown in Figure 4. Under HF + LBBB conditions (red trace), the electrical impulse spreads throughout the ventricles much slower (gradual slope) than in the healthy heart (black trace) or in CRT (green trace) configurations, completing ventricular activation after 210 ms. For CRT simulations, the rate of activated tissue was initially low, but increased rapidly to reach rates similar to those observed in healthy cases. This was especially noticeable when the LV lead was located in the epicardium (first column) and the RV lead was located in the mid and upper septum (Figure 4 (C) and (E), respectively). These results can be explained because of several factors. Firstly, the configuration of the PS and the PMJ distribution strongly affects the initial spread of the wavefront. Given the PS RV morphology, i.e. two main branches, one descending to the apex and another growing around the moderator band (Figure 1 (D)), when the RV lead was located in the apex, the electrical stimulus entered fast in the PS (around 5 ms) and propagated to remote areas faster than through the myocardium (see video 1, CRT). However, it took around 40 ms to retrogradely enter in the PS when the RV lead was located in the mid septal region, and around 90 ms when the RV lead was in the upper septum. For this reason, it took 75 ms to activate initially only 10% of the myocardium. Secondly, stimulation in the epicardial layer took longer to reach PMJ locations. Thirdly, the stimulation delay between both ventricles (VVD) also affected the initial slope of cardiac activation. Nevertheless, after 70 ms for the endocardial configurations (second column) and 125 ms for the epicardial ones the percentage of activated tissue during CRT application was higher than the percentage of HF + LBBB conditions. Moreover, during the final phase of ventricular activation, the rising rate was considerably reduced. Indeed, the electrical impulse took between 26 to 54 ms (15% to 26% of the TAT) to activate the last 10% of the ventricular tissue.

Finally, after applying the CRT protocol, the TAT was decreased by 15%, 14%, 12%, 15%, 19%, 22%, with respect to HF + LBBB conditions, as shown in Figure 5 (A) – (F), respectively. The locations of the pacing leads for the shorter QRS complexes coincided with the locations of the electrodes for the shorter TAT. However, when VVD and AVD were modified, the shortest QRS did not match the shortest TAT, which means that QRSd and TAT are not totally correlated. In addition, the difficulty in QRS measurement at the beginning and end of the signals has to be considered.

In clinical practice, a shorter QRSd is one of the standard criteria used to evaluate CRT response. However, both non-responder and responder patients show a reduction in QRSd after CRT application (Elhakam Elzoghby et al., 2017; Molhoek et al., 2004). Therefore, an additional indicator would be useful for a better perception of CRT benefit. As shown in Figure 5, TAT could be strongly modified by the initial rate of activation, as well as by the last activation interval. To avoid this, we analyzed the time elapsed to 90% of ventricular activation (t_{90}), (Figure 6). This parameter allows us to determine which configuration leads to a faster activation of most of the ventricular tissue, thus decreasing electrical dyssynchrony.

Figure 6 shows t_{90} values for a configuration with the RV lead placed in the apex, mid septum, and upper septum, and the LV lead located in the epicardium (panels (A) – (C)), and the same RV configurations with the LV located in the endocardium (panels (D) – (F)). The different delays applied

368 between the His Bundle and CRT leads (AVD) and between the RV and LV leads (VVD) are shown
369 in columns.

370 The optimal location of the LV pacing lead, both in the epicardium and endocardium, changed during
371 CRT application for each of the pacing lead locations in the RV. However, the optimal AVD and VVD
372 were the same in all cases, 140 ms and 0 ms (third column), respectively.

373 On the one hand, when AVD was modified (column 1 versus column 3 and column 2 versus column
374 4) similar results were obtained, except when the RV lead was located in the upper septum area. The
375 electrical propagation of the intrinsic stimulus contributed to decrease t_{90} (7% reduction) for an AVD
376 of 140 ms. On the other hand, when VVD was increased (column 1 versus column 2 and column 3
377 versus column 4) t_{90} increased up to 19% for all the RV lead locations.

378 When the RV lead was located in the apex, the optimal location of the LV lead in the epicardium was
379 the LV anterior wall at basal level (Figure 6 (A)). For the same RV lead location, the optimal LV lead
380 location in the endocardium was the LV posterior wall at mid-cavity level (Figure 6 (D)). Changing
381 the RV lead location to mid septum, the optimal LV lead location in the epicardium was the LV mid
382 lateral wall, while the optimal LV lead location in the endocardium was the LV mid posterior wall
383 (Figure 6 (B) and (E), respectively).

384 Finally, for the RV lead location in the upper septum, the optimal placement of the LV pacing lead in
385 the epicardium was in the LV mid lateral wall, while the optimal placement of the LV lead in the
386 endocardium was the apex of the LV lateral wall (Figure 6 (C) and (F), respectively). Table 1
387 summarizes the optimal placement of the LV lead for a faster activation of 90% of the ventricular
388 tissue. The optimal locations calculated are not in agreement with the optimal RV lead location
389 determined based on a shorter QRSd in most cases. This result suggests the hypothesis that the shortest
390 QRSd does not necessarily imply the fastest ventricular activation of 90% of the ventricular muscle.

391 **3.4 Correlation between ventricular activation and QRS**

392 To better highlight the relationship between QRSd and TAT, a correlation analysis was carried out
393 (Figure 7 (A)). Results showed an elliptical distribution of data with a moderate positive linear
394 relationship, statistically significant ($R = 0.78$ and $p < 0.05$). This moderate correlation could justify
395 the difference between the optimal AVD and VVD values for the simulations with a shortest QRSd
396 and with a shortest TAT.

397 A similar correlation analysis was made between area of the QRS (QRSa) and TAT (Figure 7 (B)). We
398 first calculated the QRSa for the average signal of the six precordial leads, between the beginning and
399 end values determined during the measurement of the QRSd. The results of the correlation show a
400 scattering distribution of data with a statistically non-significant p value ($R = -0.12$ and $p = 0.076$).
401 Thus, a linear relationship between QRSa and TAT was not observed in this study.

402 Finally, when correlating the curves of percentage of activated tissue and percentage of QRS area as a
403 function of time, a direct relationship between both variables was observed. Figure 7 (C) shows the
404 correlation between time to 90% of QRSa ($t_{90}QRSa$) and time to 90% of the ventricular activation (t_{90})
405 for each CRT simulations. A significant correlation with a high linear dependence was observed ($R =$
406 0.94 and $P < 0.05$). Simulations with shorter $t_{90}QRSa$ correspond to the simulations with shorter t_{90} .
407 Therefore, a new biomarker based on time up to 90% of the QRS area can be used as an indicator of
408 electrical synchrony.

409 4 Discussion

410 In this study, biophysical 3D multiscale simulations were conducted to assess alternative locations of
411 the RV lead for a better CRT response in LBBB HF patients. The major findings of this study can be
412 summarized as follows: i) the optimal leads location based on shortest QRS criterion was the RV upper
413 septum and the LV mid posterior region minimizing also TAT; ii) for the optimal lead location, the
414 delay configuration leading to the shortest QRSd was AVD = 140 ms, VVD = 30 ms. However, the
415 AVD and VVD setting leading to the shortest TAT was different, suggesting that minimizing QRSd is
416 a good criterion to select leads location but not to select the pacing delay; iii) the time to 90% of the
417 QRS area ($t_{90}QRSa$) was a good predictor of the instant at which 90% of the ventricular tissue had been
418 activated (t_{90}). This indicator could be used in clinical trials to complement QRSd criterion to select
419 the optimal delay of the pacing leads to obtain a faster ventricular activation of most of the ventricular
420 muscle.

421 4.1 Optimal lead location

422 The location of the optimal pacing site varies significantly between patients, so that a strategy of
423 individualized LV lead placement is required to maximize the benefit of CRT (Derval et al., 2010;
424 Spragg et al., 2010). The apex for permanent LV pacing should be avoided, as this location has been
425 associated with poor outcomes in studies such as MADIT-CRT (Singh et al., 2011; Yoshikawa et al.,
426 2010). The experimental study PATH-CHF I suggested that the mid lateral left ventricular site for the
427 LV lead may show greater acute benefit in patients with LBBB (Auricchio et al., 1999). In general, a
428 lateral or posterior vein is the desired location for achieving optimal hemodynamic support as this is
429 usually the site of most delayed activation of the left ventricular wall in patients with LBBB (Singh et
430 al., 2006; Stellbrink et al., 2000).

431 Our simulation results suggested the upper area of the RV septum as the optimal position for the RV
432 lead, in agreement with some experimental (Cano et al., 2010; Da Costa et al., 2013; Flevvari et al.,
433 2009; Muto et al., 2007) and simulation (Miri et al., 2009a) studies. The study of Leclercq and coworkers
434 (Leclercq et al., 2016) demonstrates that septal and apical RV pacing in CRT have a similar clinical
435 outcome and similar LV reverse remodeling after 6 months of therapy. However, other studies (Victor
436 et al., 2006) reported the shortest QRSd for RV septum pacing but not a better CRT response (similar
437 LVEF at 6 months). This highlights the need of additional indicators to determine the optimal
438 placement of the pacing leads.

439 In the present simulation study the most delayed activation area was located in the anterior basal LV
440 region in the HF + LBBB configuration under intrinsic activation. We also assessed the latest activated
441 area of the LV, when only RV stimulation was applied. If the RV lead was placed in the apex, the
442 anterior basal LV area was activated the latest. However, the LV lateral wall was the latest activated
443 area when the RV lead was located either in the middle or upper septal regions (see Figure S3 in
444 supplementary material).

445 The study of Zanon and coworkers (Zanon et al., 2014) determined that the LV lead location in the
446 latest activated site was predictive of the maximum increase in contractility ($LV dp/dt_{max}$). On the other
447 hand, in the recent study of Şipal and coworkers (Şipal et al., 2018), comparing the clinical benefits of
448 LV lead implantation guided by the shortest BiV-paced QRSd using surface ECG and with the standard
449 unguided CRT, there was a significantly higher rate (85% vs. 50%, $p = 0.02$) of response (>15%
450 reduction in LV end-systolic volume) to CRT as well as a shorter QRSd ($p < 0.001$) and a greater QRS
451 shortening for the surface ECG guided group. Furthermore, the optimal site for LV lead placement was
452 the posterior and posterolateral region, in agreement with our simulations. For all RV lead locations

453 tested in our study, when the LV lead was placed in the latest activated area of the LV, none of those
454 configurations led to the shortest QRSd.

455 In our study, we also showed that when pacing in the latest electrically activated area of the LV, that
456 area did not provide the shortest TAT. Similar results were observed in the simulation study by
457 Pluijmert et al. (Pluijmert et al., 2016). In that work, the authors found that the LV pacing region that
458 provided the maximum acute hemodynamic response, located near the latest activated area, did not
459 lead to the largest reduction of TAT during biventricular stimulation. Even stimulating regions leading
460 to the largest reduction of TAT showed poor increase of hemodynamic response. However, other
461 studies have found a positive correlation between acute hemodynamic response and TAT reduction
462 (Crozier et al., 2016). The optimal method to place the LV pacing lead is thus object of controversy:
463 while several studies support that pacing in the latest activated area leads to better hemodynamic
464 response, others consider the criterion of maximal reduction in QRSd as the best choice.

465 **4.2 Optimal delay between pacing leads**

466 Optimization of AVD and VVD is crucial during CRT application. A longer inter-lead electrical delay
467 was associated with more pronounced LV reverse remodeling in CRT patients with a presumed optimal
468 LV lead position concordant or adjacent to the latest mechanically activated non-scarred segment
469 (Sommer et al., 2018).

470 In clinical practice this value should be specifically set for each patient, although optimization is rarely
471 performed in the real practice. The largest trials studying CRT used various methods to optimize these
472 intervals, most frequently based on echocardiography and intracardiac electrogram interval
473 measurement, but unequivocal proof of the benefit brought by optimization is still lacking (Abraham
474 et al., 2010; Brugada et al., 2014; Krum et al., 2012). Echocardiography presents inherent variability
475 of results and is highly operator dependent (Gras et al., 2009). Optimization based on intracardiac
476 electrogram intervals has not proved yet to be of clear benefit above arbitrary AV interval (Ulč and
477 Vančura, 2013). Multisite pacing has shown favorable results, although it is technically complex
478 (Cazeau et al., 2001). A less time-consuming and easier optimization method might enable a more
479 systematic optimization of the AVD and VVD at routine follow-up visits in all recipients of CRT
480 systems.

481 The morphology of the PS clearly determined in our study the influence of AVD. When the RV lead
482 was placed in the apex, the intrinsic activation of the His bundle found the majority of the Purkinje
483 network already depolarized via retrograde conduction. However, if the RV lead was placed in the
484 middle septum or closer to the outflow tract, further from any possible entrance to the cardiac
485 conduction system, the intrinsic depolarization wavefront spread faster to the myocardium than the
486 wavefront generated through the CRT leads, leading to a reduction in TAT. Some experimental studies
487 (Prinzen and Peschar, 2002) support the idea that PS may not allow retrograde conduction in LBBB
488 patients due to structural damage, or if allowed, reduced conduction velocity would be observed in LV
489 PS sections, neglecting the influence of PS. Whether the rest of the LV branches are able to conduct
490 retrogradely (Huang et al., 2017) or other areas of the Purkinje network deteriorate, as HF evolves,
491 remains unknown. Experimental studies have measured a strong reduction in septal conduction
492 velocity during LBBB when HF was advanced compare to acute LBBB (Strik et al., 2013). In that
493 case, the simulation results of this study should be considered with caution. Although new
494 methodologies are arising to better describe the PS (Barber et al., 2018; Lee et al., 2014). The lack of
495 technology to characterize the PS in a patient specific manner, limits the optimal configuration for
496 CRT.

497 Traditional CRT pacing mode does not promote ventricular activation through conduction system from
498 the sinoatrial node. The lack of enough information on the chronic effects of the fusion leads (intrinsic
499 stimulation combined with external pacing) and this method is avoided, setting the shortest AVD based
500 on echocardiography (Barold et al., 2008). In our study, a fusion between the intrinsic activation and
501 biventricular (BiV) pacing for the optimal CRT configuration (pacing lead location and delays) was
502 assessed. Several experimental works support this procedure (Arbelo et al., 2014; Guo et al., 2015;
503 Van Gelder et al., 2005; Vatasescu et al., 2009). Guo et al. determined that congestive heart failure
504 patients with BiV pacing + intrinsic activation presented improvement in cardiac function and quality
505 of life (Guo et al., 2015). Meanwhile, Vatasescu and coworkers observed that BiV pacing fused with
506 intrinsic activation might increase the rate of structural responders (Vatasescu et al., 2009).

507 Biophysical models of the heart have been used to optimize AVD, VVD and lead location during CRT
508 simulation (Lee et al., 2017; Miri et al., 2008, 2009a, 2009b; Pluijmert et al., 2016). QRSd, estimated
509 as the difference between the time of the first and last activated cardiac cell (or TAT), have been used
510 as one optimization criterion by Miri and coworkers. In our study, the optimal LV lead location based
511 on the shortest QRSd (calculated in the ECG signal) was similar to the region with shortest TAT [see
512 Table 1]. However, VVD value that produced the shortest QRSd did not match with the VVD that
513 produced the shortest TAT, which means that QRSd and TAT are not totally correlated. A simulation
514 study by Potse and coworkers (Potse et al., 2012) support this result. The authors observed that
515 biventricular pacing did not change QRS duration but reduced total ventricular activation time when
516 the LV stimulation was applied in one point of the LV free wall.

517 **4.3 Indicators to evaluate CRT outcome**

518 The Echocardiography Guided Cardiac Resynchronization Therapy (EchoCRT) study further
519 reinforced the importance of QRSd over mechanical dyssynchrony as the most important indicator for
520 CRT responses (Ruschitzka et al., 2013). Other studies have proposed indexes based on QRS
521 measurements. Van Gelder and colleagues (Van Gelder et al., 2009) showed a relation between the Q-
522 LV interval (the interval from Q wave to intrinsic deflection on the LV EGM) and the acute
523 hemodynamic effect on optimized biventricular stimulation. A longer Q-LV interval predicted a greater
524 increase in LV pressure rise ($LVdP/dt_{max}$) and vice versa. Normalizing the QLV by QRS duration,
525 termed LV lead electrical delay (LVLED), was also shown to correlate with Doppler-derived dP/dt
526 values. LVLED greater than or equal to 50 % was associated with significantly greater reductions in
527 all-cause death or HF hospitalization at 12 months of follow-up in patients with non-ischemic
528 cardiomyopathy (Singh et al., 2006).

529 Our simulations show that the difference in QRSd was significant when the LV was paced in different
530 sites and for a fixed placement of RV. However, these differences in QRSd were decreased when
531 adjusting the delay between leads in a fixed location for both leads (see Table S1). Thus, the shortest
532 QRSd predicted precisely the region in the LV subdomains that produced the shortest TAT for the
533 three locations of the RV lead tested, leading to an increase in ventricular synchrony. However, this
534 index could not determine the pacing delay configuration between leads that allows to obtain the
535 shortest TAT. There is no consensus on how QRS should be accurately measured, and therefore small
536 differences are expected between methods (De Pooter et al., 2016). In our study, the optimal QRSd
537 obtained after CRT application supposed a 20% reduction of the QRSd. This result is in agreement
538 with the study of Elhakam et al. (Elhakam Elzoghby et al., 2017), where 180 patients under heart failure
539 conditions and LBBB were studied, and similar reductions were obtained. Other studies obtained lower
540 QRS reduction values, namely 17% and 12%, for CRT responders in Molhoek et al. (Molhoek et al.,
541 2004) and Pitzalis et al. (Pitzalis et al., 2002) studies, respectively.

542 The assessment of interventricular dyssynchrony was done analyzing the TAT. Our results showed that
543 a shorter duration of the QRS complex is moderately correlated with a shorter TAT (Figure 7 (A)). The
544 narrowest QRS complex predicted the optimal location of the stimulation leads but not the optimal
545 value of the VVD. In this way, the t_{90} index selected correctly the best delay configuration to provide
546 the fastest activation of the majority of the heart. In several configurations, TAT value was exactly the
547 same (see Table S2 in the supplementary material), but t_{90} discerned the shortest order of activation.
548 Thus, the shortest QRSd predicted the location for the optimal leads placement, but t_{90} predicted the
549 best pacing delay with the shortest TAT. We hypothesized that setting the pacing delay properly with
550 this new index could improve CRT non-responders rate.

551 Other simulation studies have assessed the evolution of TAT during CRT (Potse et al., 2012; Romero
552 et al., 2010) focused on the assessment of the LV intraventricular delay. The recent study of Tomassoni
553 (Tomassoni, 2016) showed how CRT response assessment is highly variable depending on the criteria
554 used to define the response. QRS width has been shown to correlate well with interventricular
555 dyssynchrony but unfortunately this has poor accuracy for detecting intraventricular dyssynchrony. As
556 a result, it is estimated that only 70% of patients with LBBB have echocardiographic evidence of
557 mechanical dyssynchrony (Bleeker et al., 2004). The role of mechanical dyssynchrony for improving
558 patient selection for CRT remains controversial. The multicenter, nonrandomized Predictors of
559 Response to CRT (PROSPECT) study evaluated the ability of 12 echocardiographic indices of
560 dyssynchrony to predict CRT responses at 6 months (Chung et al., 2008). These indices provided only
561 modest sensitivity and specificity, and researchers reported large variability in quantification of
562 dyssynchrony. Mechanical dyssynchrony has also been used to select CRT candidates with a narrow
563 QRS duration ≤ 120 ms, with limited success in randomized multicenter studies. In this line,
564 mechanical response generated by electrical excitation (excitation-contraction coupling) could be
565 different depending on the heart region (Gurev et al., 2010). Multiple simulation studies have addressed
566 CRT from different perspectives. The recent work of Lee et al. (Lee et al., 2018) organized and
567 summarized the state of the art of computational modeling for CRT.

568 To our knowledge, and given the benefits of using a model where all variables are accessible, our study
569 is the first to systematically explore the correlation between the activated portion of tissue (less
570 accessible in clinical practice) and the QRS complex in the torso surface. Thus, we found that an index
571 based on time to 90% of the QRS area (t_{90QRSa}) is a good predictor of the instant at which 90% of the
572 ventricular tissue has been activated (t_{90}). This indicator could be used in clinical trials to complement
573 QRSd measurements in defining the optimal location and delay of the pacing leads to produce faster
574 ventricular activation of most of the ventricular muscle.

575 **4.4 Epicardial vs Endocardial pacing**

576 Although LV epicardial stimulation decreased QRS width in most cases, a greater reduction was
577 observed for endocardial pacing. The study conducted by Spragg et al. (Spragg et al., 2010) showed
578 that CRT administered at the optimal site of the LV endocardium was more effective than stimulation
579 through an electrode in the coronary sinus. There is evidence to suggest that endocardial stimulation
580 yields to more natural transmural activation patterns and a better response for CRT patients (Behar et
581 al., 2016; Bordachar et al., 2010; Prinzen et al., 2009). In this line, new devices that allow endocardial
582 pacing and single lead stimulation (Sperzel et al., 2015) coordinated with intrinsic activation will
583 provide new possibilities.

584 The better results obtained with endocardial pacing are strongly influenced by PS. As PMJs are located
585 in the endocardial surface, the wavefront generated for the LV lead gets into the Purkinje conduction

586 system retrogradely and spreads faster to other inactivated areas (see Video 2, RETROGRADE). Thus,
587 knowing the distribution and location of PMJ, as well as the conduction system morphology is a
588 determinant factor for CRT improvement.

589 **4.5 Limitations**

590 CRT was analyzed only from an electrical point of view in our study. Mechanical behavior based on
591 echocardiography is a common alternative to assess hemodynamic response, although this method is
592 time-consuming and the optimal measurements remain unclear. Simulation studies including the
593 mechanical behavior would be certainly enlightening.

594 In this study, a particular heart geometry and PS were assessed. The inclusion or not of the moderator
595 band (which may be very patient-specific) may affect QRSd and TAT measurements, especially when
596 pacing on the RV upper septal area. Although our results have been compared to other related studies,
597 the specific findings observed in this study should be carefully validated against clinical studies and
598 complemented with a set of computational models of different patients. In addition, two isolated stimuli
599 were employed to assess CRT efficiency. The development of strategies that allow multi-site pacing
600 should be taken into account in future studies. Additionally, the incorporation of levels of HF in
601 different ventricular areas could modify simulation results.

602 **5 Conclusion**

603 In conclusion, our study showed that the optimal location for the RV lead in CRT site as an alternative
604 to RV apex, is the upper septum close to the outflow tract, based on the shortest QRSd criterion.
605 Furthermore, LV endocardial pacing leads improve CRT outcome, with respect to epicardial
606 stimulation, and areas with a higher density of PMJ are suggested for better CRT response.

607 CRT optimization based only on the shortest QRSd criterion may not be totally effective to reach the
608 maximum TAT reduction, or to optimize biventricular pacing delay. However, a biomarker based on
609 minimizing the value of t_{90} (time elapsed to 90% of ventricular activation) could be used to determine
610 the optimal VVD value. The time to reach the 90% of the QRS area ($t_{90}QRSa$) is related to the time at
611 which 90% of the ventricles are already activated (t_{90}). Thus, $t_{90}QRSa$ is suggested as an additional
612 index to assess CRT effectiveness to improve biventricular synchrony.

613 **6 Conflict of Interest**

614 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
615 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

616 **7 Author Contributions**

617 EFC, EC, JA, JF and BT contributed to the conception and design of study. ALP created the anatomical
618 model and Purkinje system was development by RS and JG. Computational simulations were
619 performed by EFC and JG. The analysis/interpretation of results was performed by EFC, JG, RS and
620 BT. All authors contributed to drafting the manuscript and all authors revised and approved the
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628 9 Abbreviations

629 AV = atrioventricular, AVD = atrioventricular delay, BiV = biventricular, CRT = cardiac
 630 resynchronization therapy, CV = conduction velocity, dV/dt_{\max} = maximum upstroke velocity, FEM =
 631 finite element method, HF = heart failure, LBBB = left bundle branch block, LV = left ventricle, LV
 632 dP/dt_{\max} = LV pressure rise, LVEF = LV ejection fraction, LVLED = LV lead electrical delay, PMJ =
 633 Purkinje myocardial junction, PS = Purkinje system, QRSa = QRS area, QRSd = QRS duration, RV =
 634 right ventricle, TAT = total ventricular activation time, t_{90} = time to 90 % of the ventricular activation,
 635 t_{90QRSa} = time to 90 % of the QRS area, VVD = interventricular delay.

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997 **Table 1.** Optimal placement of the LV lead on CRT.

LV epicardial stimulation				
Criterion	RV lead	LV lead	AVD (ms)	VVD (ms)
Shortest QRS duration	Apex	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Mid septum	Posterior - mid	140	30
	Upper septum	Posterior - mid	140	30
Shortest TAT	Apex	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Mid septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Upper septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
Faster activation of 90% of the ventricular tissue	Apex	Anterior - base	140	0
	Mid septum	Lateral - mid	140	0
	Upper septum	Lateral - mid	140	0
LV endocardial stimulation				
Criterion	RV lead	LV lead	AVD (ms)	VVD (ms)
Shortest QRS duration	Apex	Posterior - mid	100	30
	Mid septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Upper septum	Posterior - mid	140	30
Shortest TAT	Apex	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Mid septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Upper septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
Faster activation of 90% of the ventricular tissue	Apex	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Mid septum	Posterior - mid	140	0
	Upper septum	Lateral - apex	140	0

TAT = Total activation time

AVD = Atrioventricular delay

VVD = Interventricular delay

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1018 **Figure 1.** Anatomical model. (A) Biventricular hexahedral mesh of a segmented human heart. (B)
 1019 Model color-coded to show the assignment of the elements to the different cellular model in order to
 1020 model the transmural heterogeneity: endocardial cells (blue), midmyocardial cells (green) and
 1021 epicardial cells (red). (C) Arrows indicating the principal myofiber orientation of epicardial (red) and
 1022 midmyocardial (green) cells. (D) Purkinje System (PS), including three main LV branches (posterior,
 1023 septal, anterior) and RV main branches (septal and anterior). Purkinje-Junctions are represented as
 1024 magenta spheres. His Bundle, and the location of the LBBB are labeled in the model. (E) PS (black)
 1025 coupled to the biventricular model. (F) Torso model with the biventricular mesh embedded (red) and
 1026 precordial leads location (white).

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1038 **Figure 2.** Heart subdivisions and stimulation points for CRT protocol. (A) RV septal endocardial
 1039 stimulation points tested (green). (B) Left ventricular (LV) free wall region divided into three regions:
 1040 posterior (yellow), anterior (brown), and lateral (green). (C) Subdivisions of the three LV free wall
 1041 regions into nine segments. Epicardial stimulation points tested in the middle of each segment (red
 1042 dots). (D) Endocardial stimulation points tested in the LV free wall (blue dots).

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1053 **Figure 3.** Model validation. (A) Cross section of biventricular model showing color coded local
1054 activation maps of a healthy (left) and pathological heartbeat (right). (B) Precordial leads signals
1055 recorded on torso surface.

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1074 **Figure 4.** Precordial leads signals on CRT. QRS complexes in the precordial leads under HF + LBBB
 1075 conditions, before (red trace) and after (green trace) the application of the best CRT configurations
 1076 (shorter QRSd). Three different locations for the RV pacing lead were tested: RV apex with epicardial
 1077 (A) and endocardial (B) LV lead stimulation; RV mid septum with epicardial (C) and endocardial (D)
 1078 LV lead stimulation; and RV upper septum with epicardial (E) and endocardial (F) LV lead
 1079 stimulation. Stimulation points are shown in light green inside the insets for the RV lead, and in blue
 1080 and red for the LV endocardial and epicardial lead, respectively.

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1082 **Figure 5.** Cumulative frequency histograms of the normalized percentage of activated tissue. The
 1083 curves correspond to healthy (black), HF + LBBB (red) and CRT (green) scenarios. The best CRT
 1084 configurations (shortest QRSd) for the three locations of the RV lead were tested: RV apex with
 1085 epicardial (A) and endocardial (B) LV lead stimulation; RV mid septum with epicardial (C) and
 1086 endocardial (D) LV lead stimulation; and RV upper septum with epicardial (E) and endocardial (F)
 1087 LV lead stimulation.

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1093 **Figure 6.** Time to 90% of ventricular activation for the different CRT configuration delays assessed.
 1094 (A) – (C) Epicardial LV lead stimulation for the three RV lead location tested: (A) RV apex, (B) RV
 1095 mid septum and (C) RV upper septum. (D) – (F) Endocardial LV lead stimulation for the three RV
 1096 lead location tested: (D) RV apex, (E) RV mid septum and (F) RV upper septum. The three LV regions
 1097 (anterior, lateral and posterior walls) are shown in different color brightness (red, blue and yellow).
 1098 The values for healthy and HF + LBBB configurations are depicted in black and red lines respectively.

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1100 **Figure 7.** Correlation between ventricular activation and QRS. **(A)** Correlation between QRS duration
1101 and TAT (red circles show LV epicardial leads, blue circles show LV endocardial leads). **(B)**
1102 Correlation between the QRS area and TAT. **(C)** Correlation between t_{90} QRSa and t_{90} .